

Event metadata

Event title	WORKSHOP: Spatial omics sampler
Event type	Workshop
Date of event	25 February 2026
Time of event	2 - 4:30pm AEDT
Topic description	<p>This workshop provides a practical introduction to comparative analysis of spatial omics data. Starting with a pre-processed in situ spatial dataset, we will undertake some basic differential expression, look at differences of proportions of cell types, and exploratory plotting. We will work in R, using mostly Bioconductor tools. We will use a cosMx dataset, but these approaches are applicable to other technologies like Xenium or vizgen.</p> <p>Along the way we will discuss considerations specific to spatial analyses, how to scale it up to a full analysis, and how to assess our results. We will also introduce the Spatial Sampler collection of worked examples and code snippets for analyses on spatial datasets.</p>
Format description	<p>Workshop, online via Zoom over two sessions.</p> <p>Sarah Williams led the training by introducing key concepts and demonstrating the steps involved in the analysis. Participants had the option to run the code in parallel to apply these skills with support from facilitators.</p> <p>Facilitators provided assistance with exercises and answered questions in Slack in parallel to the main session</p> <p>The workshop followed the tutorial linked in the Training Materials section.</p> <p>Participation was free but subject to application with selection. Applications were reviewed by the organising committee.</p>
Identifier(s)/URL	https://www.biocommons.org.au/events/spatial-omics-sampler-workshop-2026
Licence	Materials are shared under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International agreement unless otherwise stated on the materials
Keywords	Bioinformatics http://edamontology.org/topic_0091 Analysis http://edamontology.org/operation_2945 Spatial omics
Contact	training@biocommons.org.au

Audience	This workshop is for people using or planning to use spatial transcriptomics in their work. It is suitable for newcomers to spatial analyses.
Prerequisites	<p>Recommended: basic knowledge of spatial omics technology and analysis is helpful but not essential. We recommend watching our introductory webinar Getting started with spatial omics.</p> <p>Required: R skills. While you don't need to be an expert, being able to work with tables of data, load an R library and make basic plots (ideally with ggplot2) will help you get the most out of the workshop.</p>
Technical requirements	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Slack was used to facilitate discussions. • Access to the internet, speakers, a webcam, microphone and Zoom. • Participants were provided with access to virtual machines running on ARDC Nectar Research Cloud. Packages, workflows and data were preinstalled.
Learning outcomes	<p>By the end of the workshop you should be able to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Undertake basic differential expression analysis of spatial omics data in R • Outline considerations for spatial analyses • Use Spatial Sampler to identify worked examples relevant to your work <p>This workshop will NOT cover:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • QC and filtering of the data for further analysis • PCA, UMAP and clustering analyses to group and visualise cells
Lead Trainers	Dr Sarah Williams, QCIF.
Facilitators	Fred Jaya, Sydney Informatics Hub, University of Sydney and Australian BioCommons James Sinclair, Griffith University.
Infrastructure provision	Dr Giorgia Mori, Australian BioCommons Dr Mitchell O'Brien, Sydney Informatics Hub, University of Sydney and Australian BioCommons
Training materials	<p>Training materials included in this record:</p> <p>2026-02-25 Spatial_Sampler_slides.pdf: The slides presented during this workshop</p> <p>Training materials shared elsewhere:</p> <p>Training materials including detailed notes, exercises and code</p>

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	<p>https://swbioinf.github.io/spatial-taster-workshop/</p> <p>Rmd files of R code used during the workshop via GitHub: https://github.com/swbioinf/spatial-taster-workshop</p>
Related work	<p>This workshop builds on our introductory webinar and workshop:</p> <p>‘Getting started with spatial omics’. The training materials from this webinar can be found on Zenodo: https://zenodo.org/records/17096784</p> <p>‘Spatial omics’. The training materials from this workshop can be found on Zenodo https://zenodo.org/records/18168944</p> <p>Spatial sampler - a collection of how-to guides and code snippets that we’ve developed for various tests in spatial data</p>